

5.1 WOS数据的可视化分析

李杰博士 陈超美教授

中国科学院 文献情报中心
美国德雷塞尔大学 计算与信息学院

lijie_jerry@126.com

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李杰科学网博客: <http://blog.sciencenet.cn/u/jerrycueb>

开放科学计量学学习平台: <https://www.metamatrix.cn/home>

The longer you can look back, the farther you can look forward (回顾历史越久远, 展望未来就越深远)。

Web of Science数据的处理

Web of Science数据的获取

登录web of science

Web of science为商用数据库，因此要使用该数据库需要确认所在单位已经购买。

切换到Web of Science 核心数据集

要使用citespace等科学计量与知识图谱软件分析wos数据，需要将wos切换到核心数据集。

基本检索

默认情况是基本检索方法。该方法通过字段和布尔逻辑的方式来检索数据。

结果的导出

在Web of Science中数据要保存为纯文本格式。

CiteSpace对Web of Science数据的分析

登录Web of Science文献检索平台，若默认为所有数据库，则需要将数据库切换到Web of Science核心合集。若没有切换数据库，所下载的数据将有部分字段缺失，分析过程中将存在一定的问题。

The screenshot shows the 'DOCUMENTS' tab of the Web of Science search interface. The search criteria are set to 'All Databases' and 'Collections: All'. The search box contains the text 'Example: oil spill* mediterranean'. Below the search box are buttons for '+ Add row', '+ Add date range', and 'Advanced search'. A 'Search' button is located at the bottom right of the search area. At the bottom of the page, there is a promotional banner with a bar chart icon, the text 'Jump back into your research - try out our personalized homepage dashboard.', and a 'Sign in to access' button. A link to 'Register for a new account' is also present.

The screenshot shows the 'DOCUMENTS' tab of the Web of Science search interface. The search criteria are set to 'Web of Science Core Collection' and 'Editions: All'. A dropdown menu is open, showing a list of databases: 'All Databases', 'Web of Science Core Collection', 'Current Contents Connect', 'Chinese Science Citation Database™', 'Derwent Innovations Index', 'Grants Index', 'KCI-Korean Journal Database', 'MEDLINE®', 'Preprint Citation Index', and 'ProQuest™ Dissertations & Theses Citation Index'. The 'Web of Science Core Collection' option is highlighted. To the right of the dropdown, there is a detailed description of the 'Web of Science Core Collection (1900-present)', including a search tip and a list of features: 'All cited references for all publications are fully indexed and searchable.', 'Search across all authors and all author affiliations.', 'Track citation activity with Citation Alerts.', and 'See citation activity and trends graphically with Citation Report.'. The data is noted as 'Data updated 2024-12-25'. At the bottom of the page, there is a promotional banner with a bar chart icon, the text 'Jump back into your research - try out our personalized homepage dashboard.', and a 'Sign in to access' button. A link to 'Register for a new account' is also present.

认识Web of Science核心合集

注意：各个学校购买Web of Science核心合集存在显著差异。主要表现在两个方面：1) 核心合集子数据库的类型数量；2) 子数据库的回溯时间。

The screenshot shows the 'RESEARCHERS' tab in the Web of Science interface. At the top, there are tabs for 'DOCUMENTS' and 'RESEARCHERS'. Below the tabs, there is a search bar with 'Search in: Web of Science Core Collection' and 'Editions: All'. There are also buttons for '+ Add row' and '+ Add date range'. A list of databases is displayed with checkboxes next to them, including 'Select All', 'Science Citation Index Expanded (SCI-EXPANDED)--1900-present', 'Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI)--1900-present', 'Arts & Humanities Citation Index (AHCI)--2005-present', 'Conference Proceedings Citation Index - Science (CPCI-S)--1990-present', and 'Conference Proceedings Citation Index - Social Science & (CPCI-SSH)--1991-present'. A 'Search' button is at the bottom right.

This is a close-up of the database selection list. It shows a 'Select All' checkbox at the top. Below it, several databases are listed with their respective start and end years: 'Science Citation Index Expanded (SCI-EXPANDED)--1900-present', 'Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI)--1900-present', 'Arts & Humanities Citation Index (AHCI)--2005-present', 'Conference Proceedings Citation Index - Science (CPCI-S)--1990-present', and 'Conference Proceedings Citation Index - Social Science & (CPCI-SSH)--1991-present'. The 'Arts & Humanities Citation Index (AHCI)--2005-present' is highlighted.

1900
1900
2005
1990

This is another close-up of the database selection list. It shows a 'Select All' checkbox at the top. Below it, several databases are listed with their respective start and end years: '(CPCI-SSH)--1991-present', 'Book Citation Index - Science (BKCI-S)--2005-present', 'Book Citation Index - Social Sciences & Humanities (BKCI-SSH)--2005-present', 'Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI)--2005-present', 'Current Chemical Reactions (CCR-EXPANDED)--1985-present', and 'Index Chemicus (IC)--1993-present'. The 'Index Chemicus (IC)--1993-present' is highlighted.

数据检索与下载

这里以检索论文主题涉及CiteSpace, 论文发表时间在CiteSpace发表时间范围内的论文, 时间截止到2024年。
TS=(citespace) AND FPY=2003-2024

< BACK TO BASIC SEARCHES

Advanced Search Query Builder

DOCUMENTS RESEARCHERS

Search in: Web of Science Core Collection ▾ Editions: All ▾

Add terms to the query preview

All Fields ▾ Example: liver disease india singh And ▾ Add to query

More options ▾ Search Help

Query Preview

TS=(citespace) AND FPY=2003-2024

+ Add date range × Clear Search ▾

Booleans: AND, OR, NOT Examples

Field Tags: Sort by Default ▾

- TS=Topic
- TI=Title
- AB=Abstract
- AU=[Author]
- AI=Author
- OO=Organization
- SG=Suborganization
- SA=Street Address
- CI=City
- PS=Province/State
- PMID=PubMed ID
- DOP=Publication Date
- LD=Index Date
- PUBL=Publisher

注意：在构建检索式时，一定要对所检索的文献的基本情况有所了解。这是构建检索式的前提，也是巧妙构建检索式的基础。

数据检索结果

检索结果页面显示，我们共得到了5358条记录。在我们下载数据之前，多数据的描述性统计有所了解是很有必要的。在检索结果页面的右侧，可以点击“Analyze Results”来了解所检索结果的描述性统计结果。用户可以选择Export数据导出功能，将数据导出为纯文本格式。

5,358 Documents You may also like... Analyze Results Citation Report Create Alert

Refine results Export Refine

Search within results...

Quick Filters

- Highly Cited Papers 58
- Hot Papers 3
- Review Article 1,818
- Open Access 3,839
- Enriched Cited References 1,917
- Open publisher-invited reviews 8

Publication Years ⓘ

Show Final Publication Year

- 2024 1,689
- 2023 1,442
- 2022 1,068
- 2021 427
- 2020 275

See all >

0/5,358 Add To Marked List Export ^

Sort by: Relevance < 1 of 108 >

1 How is CiteSpace used in English and Chinese? 3 Citations 19 References

2 CiteSpace: A Practical Guide to Literature 255 Citations 6 References

Export options: EndNote online, EndNote desktop, Add to my researcher profile, Plain text file, RefWorks, RIS (other reference software), BibTeX, Excel, Tab delimited file, Printable HTML file, InCites, Email, Fast 5000, More Export Options ⓘ

用于CiteSpace的数据采集

思考：若文献量大于500条的时候如何下载？

The screenshot displays the CiteSpace software interface. At the top, the search query is "TS=(citespace) AND FPY=2003-2024". Below this, there are buttons for "Add Keywords", "Quick add keywords", and "Copy query link". The main area shows "5,358 Documents" and a list of search results. An "Export Records to Plain Text File" dialog box is open, showing "Record Options" with "Records from: 1 to 500" selected. The "Record Content" dropdown is set to "Full Record and Cited References". The "Export" button is highlighted. On the right, a list of search results is visible, including titles like "Background in recent years, the impact of diet on Alzheimer's disease (AD) as a modifiable lifestyle has attracted widespread attention" and "Two decades of research on the role of diet in Alzheimer's disease (2003-2023): a bibliometric and visual analysis based on CiteSpace".

CiteSpace对数据的分析

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6.4.R1 Demo Video * CiteSpace Survey * CiteSpace Blogs

Current Versions: 6.4.R1, 6.3.R3, 6.3.R1 (Advanced)

[CiteSpace101 \(Experimental GPT\)](#) | [CiteSpace FAQ in English/Chinese \(英文/中文\)](#)

Videos: (1) [Visual Analytic Studies of Science \(2024\)](#) (2) [研究领域的形成、发展和消亡 \(2022\)](#) (3) [Delineating the Scholarly Landscape of a Research Field \(2021\)](#)

Upgrade to CiteSpace (Advanced): [1 Year on 1 Computer](#); [2 Years on 2 Computers](#)

升级高级版: 微信/支付宝 (S/¥): [1年1台电脑](#); [2年2台电脑](#)

注意: CiteSpace的官网为 [citespace.podia.com](#)。任何其它网站均未经授权。

Warning: The [citespace.podia.com](#) is the official website of CiteSpace. CiteSpace distributed on any other websites are unauthorized.

System Information

CiteSpace 6.4.R1 (64-bit) Advanced	Windows 11 (null/null)	Java 22.0.2-11 (64-bit)
Built: December 27, 2024	Processors: 16	Substrate VM
Expire: December 31, 2026	Host: 67VGMJ3 159.226.100.236	Java Home: null

Key Publications

- Chen, C. (2020) [A Glimpse of the First Eight Months of the COVID-19 Literature on Microsoft Academic Graph](#). *Front. Res. Metr. Anal.* 5:607286.
- Chen, C., Song, M. (2019) [Visualizing a field of research: A methodology of systematic scientometric reviews](#). *PLoS ONE*, 14(10):e0223994.
- Chen, C. (2017) [Science mapping: A systematic review of the literature](#). *JDIS*, 2(2), 1-40.
- Chen, C. (2016) [CiteSpace: A Practical Guide for Mapping Scientific Literature](#). Nova Science Publishers.
- Chen, C. et al. (2010) [The structure and dynamics of co-citation clusters: A multiple-perspective co-citation analysis](#). *JASIST*, 61(7), 1386-1409.
- Chen, C. (2006) [CiteSpace II: Detecting and visualizing emerging trends and transient patterns in scientific literature](#). *JASIST*, 57(3), 359-377.
- Chen, C. (2004) [Searching for intellectual turning points: Progressive Knowledge Domain Visualization](#). *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 101(Suppl.), 5303-5310.
- Chen, C. (2010) [System and method for automatically generating systematic reviews of a scientific field](#). US Patent US20110295903A1.

Acknowledgements

National Science Foundation (NSF) [SMA-1633286](#) [IIS-0612120](#), NSF/DACS-10P1303; [NEVAC](#); Thomson Reuters Citation Analysis Research Grant (2002); Elsevier; Higher Education Press; IMS Health; Pfizer; Microsoft Azure Sponsorship

This version of CiteSpace is for personal use only. Use it at your own risk.

CiteSpace 6.4.R1 (64-bit) Advanced - (c) 2003-2024 Chaomei Chen - Home: C:\Users\metascience

File Projects Data Visualization Geographical Overlay Maps Analytics Network Text Preferences Tutorials Help

Web of Science

Projects: Demo 1: Terrorism (1996-2003)

Project Home:

Data Directory:

Configuration: Source=WoS; LRF=2.5; LN=10; LBY=5; e=1.0

JVM Memory 12887 (MB) Used 0 %

Time Slicing

From 1996 JAN To 2003 DEC #Years Per Slice 1

Text Processing

Term Source

Title Abstract Author Keywords (DE) Keywords Plus (ID)

Term Type

Noun Phrases Burst Terms

Node Types

Author Institution Country Keyword Term Source Category

Reference Cited Author Cited Journal

Links

Strength Cosine Scope Within Slices

Selection Criteria

The selection uses a modified g-index in each slice: $g^2 \leq k \sum_{i \in S} c_i k_i z_i^*$

To include more or fewer nodes, increase or decrease the scale factor $k = 25$

Pruning Visualization

Pruning

Pathfinder Pruning sliced networks

Minimum Spanning Tree Pruning the merged network

打开CiteSpace后, 点击New来新建项目。

CiteSpace对数据的分析

New Project

Title: Untitled

To compute uncertainties, use the same project name in MySQL as well.

Project Home: C:\Users\metascience\citespace\Examples\Template\project

Data Directory: C:\Users\metascience\citespace\Examples\Template\data

Data Source: WoS Scopus Dimensions SZAG/MAG CNKI/WanFang CSCD CSSCI PubMed

Preferred Language: English Chinese

SO Filter: Enable Disable SC Filter: Enable Disable

LRF: Link Retaining Factor (-1: All) 2.5

L/N: Maximum Links Per Node (-1: All) 10

TopN = (n|f(n)>e) 1.0

Keyword/Term: Min Words (2) 2

Keyword/Term: Max Words (4) 4

Use Authors' Fullnames true

Use C3 true

Alias List (T/F) true

Exclusion List (T/F) true

Enable JDIC (T/F) true

Save Merged Slice (T/F) false

Node Degree Weighted (true) true

Normalize Citations Global Check

Description: How did you create the dataset?

Save Cancel

在New Project中，将项目命名为ChatGPT。
在Project Home中加载一个命名为Project的空文件。
在data Directory中加载命名为data，且包含有原始数据的文件。
Data Source默认为wos，这里不需要修改。
点击save保存新建的项目，并返回到citespace的功能参数区中。

New Project

Title: citespace

To compute uncertainties, use the same project name in MySQL as well.

Project Home: C:\Users\metascience\Desktop\citespace\project

Data Directory: C:\Users\metascience\Desktop\citespace\data

Data Source: WoS Scopus Dimensions SZAG/MAG CNKI/WanFang CSCD CSSCI PubMed

Preferred Language: English Chinese

SO Filter: Enable Disable SC Filter: Enable Disable

LRF: Link Retaining Factor (-1: All) 2.5

L/N: Maximum Links Per Node (-1: All) 10

TopN = (n|f(n)>e) 1.0

Keyword/Term: Min Words (2) 2

Keyword/Term: Max Words (4) 4

Use Authors' Fullnames true

Use C3 true

Alias List (T/F) true

Exclusion List (T/F) true

Enable JDIC (T/F) true

Save Merged Slice (T/F) false

Node Degree Weighted (true) true

Normalize Citations Global Check

Description: How did you create the dataset?

Save Cancel

参数设置与数据分析

The screenshot shows the CiteSpace 6.4.R1 Advanced interface. The window title is "CiteSpace 6.4.R1 (64-bit) Advanced - (c) 2003-2025 Chaomei Chen - Home: C:\Users\metascience". The menu bar includes File, Projects, Data, Visualization, Geographical, Overlay Maps, Analytics, Network, Text, Preferences, Tutorials, and Help.

Project Area (项目区域): A red box highlights the "Projects" section on the left. It contains a "New" button, a dropdown menu with "citespace", and "More Actions ..." buttons. Below this, the "Project Home" is set to "C:\Users\metascience\Desktop\citespace\project", the "Data Directory" is "C:\Users\metascience\Desktop\citespace\data", and the "Configuration" is "Source=WoS; LRF=2.5; L/N=10; LBY=5; e=1.0". There are "Start", "Stop", and "Reset" buttons, along with "JVM Memory 12887 (MB) Used 0 %".

Time Slicing (时区设置): A red box highlights the "Time Slicing" section at the top right. It includes a "From" dropdown set to "2005", a "To" dropdown set to "2024", and a "#Years Per Slice" dropdown set to "1".

Text Processing (功能选项): A large red box highlights the "Text Processing" section. It includes "Term Source" with checkboxes for "Title", "Abstract", "Author Keywords (DE)", and "Keywords Plus (ID)". "Term Type" has radio buttons for "Noun Phrases", "Burst Terms", and buttons for "Detect Bursts" and "Entropy". Below this, "Node Types" has radio buttons for "Author", "Institution", "Country", "Keyword", "Term", "Source", and "Category", with "Reference" selected. "Links" has a "Strength" dropdown set to "Cosine" and a "Scope" dropdown set to "Within Slices". "Selection Criteria" has tabs for "g-index", "Top N", "Top N%", "Thresholds", "Citations", "Usage180", and "Usage2013". A text box contains the formula $g^2 \leq k \sum_{i \leq g} c_i, k \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ and a scale factor $k = 25$.

Space Status (状态区域): A red box highlights the "Space Status" section on the left. It contains a text area with instructions: "Please wait while CiteSpace imports files and builds networks. Note that counts in the space column include both citer and citee entries. The process may take several minutes to complete. Similarity measure: Cosine. Link retaining factor: 2.5 times of #nodes." Below this is a table with columns "1-year slices", "criteria", "space", "nodes", and "links / all".

Pruning (Pruning): A red box highlights the "Pruning" section at the bottom. It has tabs for "Pruning" and "Visualization". Under "Pruning", there are checkboxes for "Pathfinder", "Minimum Spanning Tree", "Pruning sliced networks", and "Pruning the merged network".

项目区域

时区设置

功能选项

状态区域

CiteSpace 6.4.R1 (64-bit) Advanced - (c) 2003-2025 Chaomei Chen - Home: C:\Users\metascience

File Projects Data Visualization Geographical Overlay Maps Analytics Network Text Preferences Tutorials Help

Web of Science

Projects: citespace

Project Home: C:\Users\metascience\Desktop\citespace\project

Data Directory: C:\Users\metascience\Desktop\citespace\data

Configuration: Source=WoS; LRF=2.5; L/N=10; LBY=5; e=1.0

JVM Memory 12887 (MB) Used 2 %

Space Status

2014	g=34, k=25	199	34	85 / 113
2015	g=39, k=25	342	39	81 / 81
2016	g=33, k=25	374	33	73 / 73
2017	g=54, k=25	866	54	135 / 148
2018	g=70, k=25	1587	70	175 / 323
2019	g=110, k=25	3707	110	275 / 1005
2020	g=115, k=25	5640	115	287 / 775
2021	g=153, k=25	11761	153	382 / 1504
2022	g=259, k=25	32685	259	647 / 4233
2023	g=283, k=25	45094	283	707 / 4794
2024	g=309, k=25	56967	309	772 / 4916

Process Reports

20 Review; Book Chapter
40 Review; Retracted Publication

Distinct references [Valid]: 287411 99.4925%
Distinct references [Invalid]: 1466 0.5075%

Parsing Time: 2 minutes 58.977997 seconds
Total Run time: 3 minutes 1.449997 seconds

Merged network: Nodes=1036, Links=3900
Exclusion List: 0
Network modeling ends at Thu Jan 09 14:36:54 CST 2025.

Time Slicing

From 2005 JAN To 2024 DEC #Years Per Slice 1

Text Processing

Term Source
 Title Abstract Author Keywords (DE) Keywords Plus (ID)

Term Type
 Noun Phrases Burst Terms

Node Types

Author Institution Country Keyword Term Source Category

Reference Cited Author Cited Journal

Links

Strength Cosine Scope Within Slices

Selection Criteria

The selection uses a modified g-index in each slice: $g^2 \leq k \sum_{i \in g} c_i, k \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

To include more or fewer nodes, increase or decrease the scale factor k = 25

Pruning Visualization

Pruning

Pathfinder Pruning sliced networks
 Minimum Spanning Tree Pruning the merged network

Your Options

? Project Title: citespace

Time Frame: 2005-2024
Qualified Records: 5333

How do you like to proceed?

Visible	Count	Centra...	Year	Cited References
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	446	0.00	2019	Chen CM, 2019, PLOS ON...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	271	0.00	2021	Donthu N, 2021, J BUS R...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	266	0.00	2017	Chen CM, 2017, J DATA IN...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	166	0.00	2022	Ninkov A, 2022, PERSPEC...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	139	0.00	2021	Sung H, 2021, CA-CANCE...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	121	0.00	2021	Ma D, 2021, FRONT IMMU...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	110	0.00	2019	Liu S, 2019, NEURAL RE...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	108	0.00	2022	Ding X, 2022, ELECTRON ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	100	0.00	2021	Wu HY, 2021, FRONT ME...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	93	0.00	2017	Liang YD, 2017, J PAIN R...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	92	0.00	2021	Kokol P, 2021, HEALTH IN...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	91	0.00	2019	Brandt JS, 2019, JAMA NE...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	90	0.00	2020	Ke LX, 2020, FRONT PHA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	89	0.00	2017	Aria M, 2017, J INFORMET...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	80	0.00	2018	Hou JH, 2018, SCIENTOM...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	77	0.00	2021	Zhang J, 2021, FRONT O...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	77	0.00	2020	Unknown -, 2020, CA CAN...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	76	0.00	2020	Chen Chaomei, 2020, FR...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	75	0.00	2018	Liao HC, 2018, SUSTAINA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	75	0.00	2018	Fang Y, 2018, J SUSTAIN ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	73	0.00	2022	Liu XC, 2022, BIOSENS BI...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	73	0.00	2019	Gao Y, 2019, INT IMMUNO...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	69	0.00	2020	Qin Y, 2020, BRAIN RES B...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	68	0.00	2022	Zhong DL, 2022, FRONT ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	68	0.00	2022	Sabe M, 2022, NEUROSCI...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	67	0.00	2021	Ma CQ, 2021, FRONT ON...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	67	0.00	2017	Li XJ, 2017, INT J HOSP M...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	66	0.00	2022	Arruda H, 2022, J MED LIB...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	65	0.00	2021	Wu HY, 2021, ARCH OST...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	65	0.00	2019	Huang XQ, 2019, J TRANS...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	65	0.00	2020	Moral-Muñoz JA, 2020, PR...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	64	0.00	2022	Shen JM, 2022, FRONT IM...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	61	0.00	2020	Yao LM, 2020, CHEMOSP...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	60	0.00	2018	Pan XL, 2018, J INFORME...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	59	0.00	2022	Chen YX, 2022, CHEMOS...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	58	0.00	2017	Yu DJ, 2017, INFORM SCI...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	57	0.00	2020	Chen XY, 2020, TRANSPO...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	57	0.00	2018	Olawumi TO, 2018, J CLE...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	55	0.00	2022	Wu FP, 2022, FRONT IMM...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	55	0.00	2021	Luo HF, 2021, FRONT PS...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	55	0.00	2020	Zhang XL, 2020, FOODS, ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	54	0.00	2021	Ma D, 2021, FRONT CAR...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	52	0.00	2020	Birkle C, 2020, QUANT SC...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	51	0.00	2021	Wang S, 2021, FRONT IM...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	50	0.00	2018	Ouyang W, 2018, SCI TOT...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	50	0.00	2019	Roldan-Valadez E, 2019, I...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	48	0.00	2021	Wilson M, 2021, JAMA NE...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	48	0.00	2019	Zheng KY, 2019, MED SCI ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	47	0.00	2019	Shi YL, 2019, SUSTAINABI...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	47	0.00	2022	Sun HL, 2022, FRONT IM...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	47	0.00	2022	Cheng KM, 2022, FRONT ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	45	0.00	2019	Su XW, 2019, SAGE OPEN...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	45	0.00	2021	Ahmad P, 2021, PERIODO...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	44	0.00	2021	Page MJ, 2021, BMJ-BRIT ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	43	0.00	2021	Singh VK, 2021, SCIENTO...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	43	0.00	2022	Shen ZF, 2022, FRONT O...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	42	0.00	2014	Chen CM, 2014, EXPERT...

Spotlight Show/Hide Citation/Frequency Burst >>> <<< Search: ti:q1 | fu:* # clusters

Control Panel

Colormap Burstness Search Clusters

Labels Layout Views

Keyword | Term | Overlay Labels

By Degree Show Frequency

Threshold

Font Size

Node Size

Node Labels

By Citation Show Frequency

Threshold

Font Size

Node Size

Link Labels

Show Link Labels Show Link Strengths

Font Size

Cluster Labels

Threshold

Font Size

Show Cluster Labels Over Time

Max Length

Minimizing Overlaps

Cluster Labels Node Labels

Visible	Count	Centra...	Year	Cited References
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	446	0.00	2019	Chen CM, 2019, PLOS ON...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	271	0.00	2021	Donthu N, 2021, J BUS R...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	266	0.00	2017	Chen CM, 2017, J DATA IN...
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<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	42	0.00	2014	Chen CM, 2014, EXPERT ...

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 January 9, 2025, 2:33:21 PM CST
 WoS: C:\Users\metascience\Desktop\citespace\data
 TImespan: 2005-2024 (Slice Length=1)
 Selection Criteria: g-index (k=25), LRF=1.0
 Network: N=1036, E=3900 (Density=0.376)
 Largest 1 CCs: 807 (77%)
 Nodes Labeled: 1.0%
 Pruning: None
 Modularity Q=0.673
 Weighted Mean Silhouette S=0.8369
 Harmonic Mean(Q, S)=0.7461

Control Panel

Colormap Burstness Search Clusters

Labels Layout Views

Keyword | Term | Overlay Labels

By Degree Show Frequency

Threshold

Font Size

Node Size

Node Labels

By Cluster Show Frequency

Threshold

Font Size

Node Size

Link Labels

Show Link Labels Show Link Strengths

Font Size

Cluster Labels

Threshold

Font Size

Show Cluster Labels Over Time

Max Length

Minimizing Overlaps

Cluster Labels Node Labels

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<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	446	0.00	2019	Chen CM, 2019, PLOS ON...
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Control Panel

Colormap | Burstness | Search | Clusters

Labels | Layout | Views

Keyword | Term | Overlay Labels

By Degree Show Frequency

Threshold: 10

Font Size: 5

Node Size: 1

Node Labels

By Cluster Show Frequency

Threshold: 2

Font Size: 5

Node Size: 8

Link Labels

Show Link Labels Show Link Strengths

Font Size: 8

Cluster Labels

Threshold: 0

Font Size: 16

Show Cluster Labels Over Time

Max Length: 150

Minimizing Overlaps

Cluster Labels Node Labels

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Spotlight Show/Hide Citation/Frequency Burst >>> <<< Search: ti:q1 | fu:* # clusters 89

Control Panel

Colormap Burstness Search Clusters

Labels Layout Views

Keyword | Term | Overlay Labels

By Degree Show Frequency

Threshold 2

Font Size 5

Node Size 3

Node Labels

By Cluster Show Frequency

Threshold 2

Font Size 22

Node Size 12

Link Labels

Show Link Labels Show Link Strengths

Font Size 8

Cluster Labels

Threshold 0

Font Size 16

Show Cluster Labels Over Time

Max Length 150

Minimizing Overlaps

Cluster Labels Node Labels

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Spotlight Show/Hide Citation/Frequency Burst >>> Search: ti:q1 | fu:* # clusters 89

Control Panel

Colormap Burstness Search Clusters

Labels Layout Views

Keyword | Term | Overlay Labels

By Degree Show Frequency

Threshold

Font Size

Node Size

Node Labels

By Cluster Show Frequency

Threshold

Font Size

Node Size

Link Labels

Show Link Labels Show Link Strengths

Font Size

Cluster Labels

Threshold

Font Size

Show Cluster Labels Over Time

Max Length

Minimizing Overlaps

Cluster Labels Node Labels

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<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	42	0.00	2014	Chen CM, 2014, EXPERT...

CiteSpace, v. 5.4.R1 (64-bit) Advanced ✓
 January 9, 2025, 3:05:28 PM CST
 WoS: C:\Users\metascience\Desktop\citespace\data
 Timespan: 2005-2024 (Slice Length=1)
 Selection Criteria: g-index (k=25), LRF=2.5, L/N=10, LBγ=5, ee=1.0
 Network: N=1036, E=3900 (Density=0.0073)
 Largest 1 CCs: 907 (77%)
 Nodes Labeled: 1.0%
 Pruning: None
 Modularity Q=0.673
 Weighted Mean Silhouette S=0.8369
 Harmonic Mean(Q, S)=0.7461

Search: ti:q1 | fu:* # clusters 89

Control Panel

Colormap Burstness Search Clusters

Labels Layout Views

Keyword | Term | Overlay Labels

By Degree Show Frequency

Threshold 10

Font Size 5

Node Size 1

Node Labels

By Cluster Show Frequency

Threshold 2

Font Size 5

Node Size 10

Link Labels

Show Link Labels Show Link Strengths

Font Size 8

Cluster Labels

Threshold 0

Font Size 23

Show Cluster Labels Over Time

Max Length 150

Minimizing Overlaps

Cluster Labels Node Labels

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Control Panel

Colormap Burstness Search Clusters

Labels Layout Views

Colormap

Transparency

Node Alpha: 29

Node Label Alpha: 80

Lower Bound Label Alpha: 168

Link Alpha: 19

Area Fillcolor Alpha: 29

Cluster Label Alpha: 80

Sub-Cluster Label Alpha: 80

Guiding Line Alpha: 0

Monochrome Snapshot Spotlight

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<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	42	0.00	2014	Chen CM, 2014, EXPERT...

Spotlight Show/Hide Citation/Frequency Burst >>> Search: ti:q1 | fu:* # clusters 89

#0 scientometric analysis

#1 using citespace

#2 mapping trend

#3 quantum computing

#4 bibliometric overview

#5 intellectual structure

#6 regenerative medicine

#7 emerging trend

#12 document co-citation analysis

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Spotlight Show/Hide Citation/Frequency Burst >>> Search: ti:q1 | fu:* # clusters 591

Control Panel

Colormap Burstness Search Clusters

Labels Layout Views

Keyword | Term | Overlay Labels

By Freq Show Frequency

Threshold

Font Size

Node Size

Node Labels

By Citation Show Frequency

Threshold

Font Size

Node Size

Link Labels

Show Link Labels Show Link Strengths

Font Size

Cluster Labels

Threshold

Font Size

Show Cluster Labels Over Time

Max Length

Minimizing Overlaps

Cluster Labels Node Labels

元宇宙论文数据的可视化分析

当前Metaverse核心知识基础的结构

distance seminar ; complementing classroom teaching; educational innovation. 服务元宇宙(远程研讨会、补充课堂教学、医疗等)

营销元宇宙

虚拟世界技术

教育元宇宙

扩展现实与混合现实

Extended Reality; Metaverse Context
Mixed Reality; Video Game
Digital Twin Technology Trend; Geoscience

Online Education; 3d Digital Virtual World; Virtual World

Adaptive Fuzzy Knowledge-based System; Control Metabots Mobility; Virtual Environment

New emerge co-citation links in 2021 (2021年Metaverse研究新建的共被引链接)

New emerge co-citation links in 2022 (2022 年Metaverse研究新建的共被引链接)

Citing terms in # 0: extended reality; metaverse context; service experience research; novel method; virtual commerce application design.

其他案例

其他案例：锂电池热失控研究

Academic Integrity

- ✓ Various contexts
- ✓ Psychology of dishonest behaviors
- ✓ Social comparisons
- ✓ Controversial: some forms of dishonesty can lead to positive outcomes or creativity

- ✓ Online and distance learning
- ✓ Impact of COVID-19
- ✓ Proctoring tools
- ✓ Cultural attitudes

Creativity (创造力)

- #0
- #1
- #2
- #3
- #4
- #5
- #6
- #7
- #8
- #9

CiteSpace (1/1/2004-7/31/2023): depicted: 23,901 (98%) of the co-citation network of 24,171 unique references cited by 9,394 articles. Clusters: 197, Modularity: 0.6865, Weighted Mean Silhouette: 0.8723. from Chaomei

A network of co-cited references generated by CiteSpace 6.2.R4 (Advanced). Selection Criteria: Top 100.0% per slice, up to 1,000, LRF=-1, L/N=-1, LBY=-1, e=0.0 Network: N=11,877, E=487,891, LCC=11,852 (99%) Modularity Q=0.7082, Weighted Mean Silhouette S=0.8916, H. Mean=0.7894

An Intellectual Landscape

A Co-Citation Network
(1991-2004)

My 7/24 keynote at the 28th Int'l Conf. on Information Visualisation, Coimbra, Portugal.

Title: A Visual Exploration of the Intellectual Landscape of Information Visualization: Hindsight, Insight, and Foresight

Slides: <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21672.17929>; Conference: <https://lnkd.in/g/FNRahhK> From Chaomei

CiteSpace学习文献

李杰, 陈超美. CiteSpace科技文本挖掘及可视化(第四版)[M]. 首都经济贸易大学出版社. 2025.

声明：该电子课件为《CiteSpace科技文本挖掘及可视化》的配套电子课件，请合理使用。

科学计量与知识图谱系列丛书

丛书主编：李杰

CiteSpace:

Text mining and

Visualization in Scientific Literature (Fourth Edition)

CiteSpace:

科技文本挖掘及可视化

(第四版)

李杰 陈超美 著

随着信息技术的飞速进步，**可视化**应用越来越普及，今后的学习越来越多地借助各种可视化手段，视觉器官将发挥前所未有的作用。

可视化方式成为主流学习方式后，人类的学习效率将大大提高，有可能带来一场认知革命。

首都经济贸易大学出版社
Capital University of Economics and Business Press

Home History MOOC Books Journals Tools Scholars Gallery Links Metasciences Safemetrics About

Open Scientometrics Learning Platform
开放科学计量学学习平台

科学计量学理论与工具视频

MOOC for Scientometrics Theories and Tools

开放科学计量学视频号

什么是科学计量学 (AI生成)

CiteSpace理论与实践
(主讲人：陈超美、李杰)
链接1 链接2 链接3

陈超美 科学网博客
点击前往博客 →

李杰 科学网博客
点击前往博客 →

武夷山 科学网博客
(课外学习推荐)
点击前往博客 →

什么是文献计量学?

文献计量学的局限性

库恩的科学革命

什么是文献共被引?

文献计量学与可视化

库恩的常规科学

《自然》150年 引文空间网络

引文分析的历史

第一届MKD珍贵视频

引文索引50年

科学学导论

负责任的科学计量学

开放科学计量学学习平台：<https://www.metamatrix.cn/mooc>

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